

NEGATIVE PARTICLES IN ARABIC AND THEIR EFFECT ON NOUNS.

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Abstract. The purpose of writing this article is to shed light on the changes that occur in sentences, the formation of negation and absolute negation in Arabic . Analyzing how and in what way it is expressed from the point of view of Arabic linguistics, and the main goal of this work is to show the place of negative charges in the sentence and the places of its application

Key words : negative words, negative prepositions, noun, adjective, number, participle clause, la negative preposition, ma negative preposition, bi preposition, gayrun-negative word, absolute negative

In Arabic, negative words are completely different from negative words in Uzbek. In Uzbek, negative words come after the negative words, and in Arabic, negative prepositions always come before the negative words. Those in the tune of downloads that mean negation

la not, no	لا
not, no ma	ما
lam	لم
lan	لن
kalla	كلا

These prepositions are also used to form negative forms of nouns, adjectives, and verbs. In this article, the two most commonly used of these prepositions are ma ما لا لا la.

ma negative predicate is used to form the negative form of the past tense verb. for example:

Salim did not come to school.

المدرسة الى سليم وصل ما

Ma vasala Salum ilal maktaba _

In addition, this predicate is also used to negate the participle of a nominal (noun participle in Uzbek) sentence. In this case, if the participle of the noun phrase is represented by a noun phrase, in the accusative case, it is expressed by an adjective phrase .bi ب is in karatkich agreement with its preposition. For example: There is nothing surprising about it.

عجيباً شيئاً فيه ما Ma fixi shay'an ajiban.

Another interesting aspect is that if lacomes before the verb, the actions at the end of the verbs do not change in the present future tense. When the imperative negative form of the verb is formed, the last action in the negative imperative form that comes after the negative charge of لا la is silent. for example:

you write tktb ANTAnta taktubu

Sen yozayapsan انت تكتب Anta taktubu

Another strange thing is that the لا negative charge comes with the word "غير" and the meaning of the charge "la" is given as a positive one.

سليم غير هذا يعلم لا

a ya'lamu khaza goyru Salimin .

This only Salim knows .

It would not be wrong to interpret it as nobody knows except Salim.

negative charge sometimes also expresses absolute negation. For example:

لا رجل فيل غرفة la rajula fil gurfati There is no one in the room

لا حول و لا قوة فيه la khawla wa la kuwwata fixi . There is no force and no force in this

The negation case la, which expresses absolute negation, requires that the possessive that comes after it must come in the negative case, i.e., without the article al, in the negative case without negation.

Somehow in scores participle of the sentence part down is lifted . for example

that's it la basa لا باس that translation is Never mind What else ? came ?

ما لك ma laka what happened with you?

ما هذا ma haza what is it? _

Ma laka likhazar rajuli ? ما لك لهذا الرجل؟ With this person what do you have a job

Ma takunu anta min khazikhil mar'ati ما تكون انت من هذه المرأة

ما الخبر mal khobaru what did it happen ? what news ?

ما denial download infernal with together it's the same like a field translation is worn

ما العمل ma al amalu? what to do

The negative charge sometimes means something

wasafa ma khadasa dissolved whatever happened.

عالم بعد الحرب a'lamun ma badal harbi world after the war.

ما also used in sentences where the owner is unknown. for example:

على ما يقال هذا الرجل من القاهرة ala ma yukolu Khazar rojulu minal kohirati

as they say this person is from Cairo it is

ma denial download time also comes to express i.e time is also used in expressions , for example :

يوم ما رايته ywm ma raith don't ma report the day I built it

مطر ح ما رايته matrokhu ma lucky the place I met you _

و ما ان اقترب منها حتى قالت w ma an aqtrb mná hty qaltand ma in iktaraba Minha big case

It was only when he approached her that he said ael..

ما ma denial download a tree talk denial the meaning in notification is used , for example :

و ما لنا نذهب بعيدا wand ma lana nazkhabu

we far away we don't go need two to us far away to go need load _

What else ? which is is also used in meanings

كتاب ما the book ma somehow book _

هنا مخزن ما huna makhzanun ma This is what it is there is a shop.

ما دمت حيا ma tail haiyan I am a hater

لا اوفق هذا ما اختلف الليل والنهر la uvafiku khaza ma conflict laylu van naharu

I to this never when I don't agree .

ما ma denial download in the sentence look at the meaning again no , it doesn't count

translated as _ is worn . Talk about it noun section uncertain in case that is, without the article

al revenue in agreement stands two prepositions (fore helper with uncertain in case in

agreement stands _

ما هو عدوا ma huwa aduvvan He is not an enemy .

ما هو بعدو ma huwa biaduvvin He is not an enemy .

When the negative preposition من comes with the interrogative predicate, it also means no one, no one, no one, for example.

المسألة من واحد فسرلنا هذه المسألة ma man vakhidun fassara lana khazikhil mas'alata

Someone should explain this matter to us, and no one should explain this matter to us.

ما اذا ma iza

ma denial download iza a must download with come probability , uncertainty means _

وانها لا تدري ما اذا كان يفهمها Inna kha la tadri ma iza kana yafhamukha

she is a woman, he doesn't know if he understands her or not.

رب rubba When it comes with a particle, it also means probability, for example::

ربما rubba

to be that maybe _ translation is that is be .

ربما وصل بعد الظهر rubba and so on badass zukhri

perhaps from a dream after may have come two from the dream after came to be can _

لا particle of negation comes with the particle of proof in which it is crushed by the particle of proof

هلا اخبرتني كم السعة الان aunt information kamis sa'atu alana.

telling give Can't you get it now ? hour how many became two now hour how many that it was say can't you

هلا بخت بهذا السر halla bukhta bi khazas the secret

this the secret to me say can you two this the secret to me open can you

لا لا

no.... , ...you, meaning anti (against) as well comes , for example :

لا حزبي la hizbiyyun without a party .

لا محدود la mahdudun limitless i.e no points

لا مسؤولون I I a is responsible irresponsible .

لا قانوني It's legal illegal _

la negation Preposition bi preposition (perfick) with will come and by that..you mean translation is used , for example :

شربت الشاي بلا السكر sharibtush shaya you know sukkar I drank tea without sugar

عالم بلا عمل كشاب بلا alimun bila amalin ka sahabin bila matorin .

Without I scientist poor cloud _ Without I the scientist thinks that or not _ _ like a cloud

وعد بلا وفاق عداوة بلا سبب va'dun bila vafa'in adavatun bila sababin

. Unfaithful a promise without reason is enmity .

لان انلا la

la negation download to the owner effect the recipient inna download with come , ... other , out of ... that translation is worn .

وصل جميع الطلاب الا محمود and so on community tullabu ill Makhmudin

From Mahmud another all students they came

ذهب جميع الطلاب الا سليم zahaba jami'u t ' t u llabu illa Salimin .

From Salim out all workers to the factory they left

download la follow sentences in the composition comes , is counted , ... say translated as _ is used , for example :

فهي التين الذي لا يشبع و البئر التي لا تمتلئ professional _ tinninul lazi la yashba'u val bi'rul lati la tamtali'u .

He (war) felt not available dragon , stuffed not available the well is counted .

(War pretending can't find dragon , stuffed can't find is a well).

ma download desire you want denial the meaning kham is used in expression , in which ليت lyt
lay water with together will come for example

هذا هونعم نعم . هذا هو و يا ليت ما كان

khaza khuva , na'am , na'am , khaza khuva . and ya laitahu I don't know.

Yes, it is yes , yes, yes this that's it . I wish he hadn't was _

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